

SOME PROPERTIES OF NEW GENERALIZED CLOSED SETS WITH RESPECT TO IDEAL TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

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Abstract

The main focus of this study is to introduce a new category of generalized closed sets, referred to as \mathcal{J} -closed sets, within the framework of with respect to ideal topological spaces. I investigate the relationship between the class of closed sets and the class of \mathcal{J} -closed sets.

Keywords: \mathcal{J} -closed, $\mathcal{J}\alpha$ -closed, I_g -cld, I - \hat{g} -closed.

1. Introduction

S. Jafari and N. Rajesh [7], introduced the generalized closed sets with respect to an ideal. In 1970, N. Levine [8], introduced the generalized closed sets in topology and K. Kuratowski [6], introduced topology. A. Acikgoz and et al. [1], introduced the on α -I-continuous and α -I-open functions.

The main focus of this study is to introduce a new category of generalized closed sets, referred to as \mathcal{J} -closed sets, within the framework of with respect to ideal topological spaces. I investigate the relationship between the class of \star -closed sets and the class of \mathcal{J} -closed sets.

2. Preliminaries

An ideal I on a topological space (briefly, TPS) X is an on empty collection of subsets of X which satisfies

- (1) $M \in I$ and $N \subseteq M \Rightarrow N \in I$ and
- (2) $M \in I$ and $N \in I \Rightarrow M \cup N \in I$.

Given a topological space (X, τ) with an ideal I on X if $\mathcal{P}(X)$ is the set of all subsets of X , a set operator $(\bullet)\star: \mathcal{P}(X) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(X)$, called a local function [4] of M with respect to τ and I is defined as follows: for $M \subseteq X$, $M\star(I, \tau) = \{x \in X: U \cap M \notin I \text{ for every } U \in \tau(x)\}$ where $\tau(x) = \{U \in \tau: x \in U\}$. A Kuratowski closure operator $cl\star(\bullet)$ for a topology $\tau\star(I, \tau)$, called the \star -topology and finer than τ , is defined by $cl\star(M) = M$

$\cup M\star(I, \tau)$ [4]. We will simply write $M\star$ for $M\star(I, \tau)$ and $\tau\star$ for $\tau\star(I, \tau)$. If I is an ideal on X , then (X, τ, I) is called an ideal topological space (briefly, ITPS). A subset M of an ideal topological space (X, τ, I) is \star -closed (briefly, \star -closed) [4] if $M\star \subseteq M$. The interior of a subset M in $(X, \tau\star(I))$ is denoted by $int\star(M)$.

Definition 2.1 A subset P of a TPS X is called:

- (i) semi-open set [2] if $P \subseteq cl(int(P))$;
- (ii) α -open set [9] if $P \subseteq int(cl(int(P)))$;
- (iii) β -open set (Semi-pre-open) [2] if $P \subseteq cl(int(cl(P)))$;

Definition 2.2 A subset P of a TPS X is called

- (i) α gs-closed (briefly, α gs-cld) [9] if $\alpha\text{cl}(P) \subseteq Q$ whenever $P \subseteq Q$ and Q is semi-open.
- (ii) semi-generalized closed (briefly, sg-cld) [2] if $\text{scl}(P) \subseteq Q$ whenever $P \subseteq Q$ and Q is semi-open.
- (iii) ψ -closed (briefly, ψ -cld) [11] if $\text{scl}(P) \subseteq Q$ whenever $P \subseteq Q$ and Q is sg-open.
- (iv) generalized semi-closed (briefly, gs-cld) [10] if $\text{scl}(P) \subseteq Q$ whenever $P \subseteq Q$ and Q is open.
- (v) α -generalized closed (briefly, α g-cld) [9] if $\alpha\text{cl}(P) \subseteq Q$ whenever $P \subseteq Q$ and Q is open.
- (vi) generalized semi-pre-closed (briefly, gsp-cld) [10] if $\text{spcl}(P) \subseteq Q$ whenever $P \subseteq Q$ and Q is open.

Definition 2.3 A subset P of a ITPS X is called

- (i) I_g -closed (briefly, I_g -cld) set [3] if $P^* \subseteq Q$ whenever $P \subseteq Q$ and Q is open.
- (ii) $I\hat{g}$ -closed (briefly, $I\hat{\omega}$ -cld) [5] if $P^* \subseteq Q$ whenever $P \subseteq Q$ and Q is semi-open.

3. \mathcal{J}^* -CLOSED SETS

Definition 3.1 A subset P of X is called

- (i) \mathcal{J}^* -closed (briefly, \mathcal{J}^* -cld) if $P^* \subseteq Q$ whenever $P \subseteq Q$ and Q is sg-open. The complement of \mathcal{J}^* -closed is called \hat{I} -open.
- (ii) \mathcal{J}^* α -closed (\mathcal{J}^* α -cld) if $\alpha\text{cl}(P^*) \subseteq Q$ whenever $P \subseteq Q$ and Q is sg-open.

The complement of \mathcal{J}^* α -closed is called \mathcal{J}^* α -open.

Proposition 3.2

Every \star -closed is \mathcal{J}^* -cld but converse is not true.

Proof

If P is any \star -closed in X and K is any sg-open set containing P , then $K \supseteq P = P^*$. Hence P is \mathcal{J}^* -cld.

Example 3.3

Let $X = \{p_1, q_1, r_1\}$, $\tau = \{\phi, \{p_1, q_1\}, X\}$ and $\mathcal{J} = \{\phi\}$. Then $\mathcal{J}^* \text{-C}(X) = \{\phi, \{r_1\}, \{p_1, r_1\}, \{q_1, r_1\}, X\}$. Here, $P = \{p_1, r_1\}$ is \mathcal{J}^* -cld but not \star -closed.

Proposition 3.4

Every \mathcal{J}^* -cld is \mathcal{J}^* α -cld but converse is not true.

Proof

If P is a \mathcal{J}^* -cld subset of X and K is any sg-open set containing P , then $K \supseteq P^* \supseteq \alpha\text{cl}(P^*)$. Hence P is \mathcal{J}^* α -cld.

Example 3.5

Let $X = \{p_1, q_1, r_1\}$, $\tau = \{\phi, \{q_1\}, X\}$ with $\mathcal{J} = \{\phi\}$. Then $\mathcal{J}^* \text{C}(X) = \{\phi, \{p_1, r_1\}, X\}$ and $\mathcal{J}^* \alpha \text{C}(X) = \{\phi, \{p_1\}, \{r_1\}, \{p_1, r_1\}, X\}$. Here, $P = \{p_1\}$ is \mathcal{J}^* α -cld but not \mathcal{J}^* -cld.

Proposition 3.6

Every \mathcal{J}^* -cld is ψ -cld but converse is not true.

Proof

If P is a \mathcal{J}^* -cld subset of X and K is any sg-open set containing P , then $K \supseteq P^* \supseteq \text{scl}(P)$. Hence P is ψ -cld.

Example 3.7

Let $X = \{p_1, q_1, r_1\}$, $\tau = \{\phi, \{p_1\}, X\}$ and $\mathcal{J} = \{\phi\}$. Then $\mathcal{J}^*C(X) = \{\phi, \{q_1, r_1\}, X\}$ and $\psi C(X) = \{\phi, \{q_1\}, \{r_1\}, \{q_1, r_1\}, X\}$. Here, $P = \{q_1\}$ is ψ -cld but not \mathcal{J}^* -cld.

Proposition 3.8

Every \mathcal{J}^* -cld is \mathcal{J} - ω -cld but converse is not true.

Proof

Suppose that $P \subseteq K$ and K is semi-open in X . Since every semi-open is sg-open and P is \mathcal{J}^* -cld. Therefore $P^* \subseteq K$. Hence P is \mathcal{J} - ω -cld.

Example 3.9

Let $X = \{p_1, q_1, r_1, s_1\}$, $\tau = \{\phi, \{s_1\}, \{q_1, r_1\}, \{q_1, r_1, s_1\}, X\}$ and $\mathcal{J} = \{\phi\}$. Then $\mathcal{J}^*C(X) = \{\phi, \{p_1\}, \{p_1, s_1\}, \{p_1, q_1, r_1\}, X\}$ and \mathcal{J} - $\omega C(X) = \{\phi, \{p_1\}, \{p_1, q_1\}, \{p_1, r_1\}, \{p_1, s_1\}, \{p_1, q_1, r_1\}, \{p_1, q_1, s_1\}, \{p_1, r_1, s_1\}, X\}$. Here, $P = \{p_1, r_1, s_1\}$ is \mathcal{J} - ω -cld but not \mathcal{J}^* -cld.

Proposition 3.10

Every \mathcal{J}^* -cld is I_g -cld but converse is not true.

Proof

If P is a \mathcal{J}^* -cld subset of X and K is any open set containing P , since every open set is sg-open, we have $K \supseteq P^*$. Hence P is I_g -cld.

Example 3.11

Let $X = \{p_1, q_1, r_1\}$, $\tau = \{\phi, \{p_1\}, \{q_1, r_1\}, X\}$ and $\mathcal{J} = \{\phi\}$. Then $\mathcal{J}^*C(X) = \{\phi, \{p_1\}, \{q_1, r_1\}, X\}$ and $I_gC(X) = P(X)$. Here, $P = \{p_1, q_1\}$ is I_g -cld but not \mathcal{J}^* -cld.

Proposition 3.12

Every \mathcal{J}^* -cld is αg_s -cld but converse is not true.

Proof

If P is a \mathcal{J}^* -cld subset of X and K is any semi-open set containing P , since every semi-open set is sg-open, we have $K \supseteq P^* \supseteq \alpha \text{cl}(P^*)$. Hence P is αg_s -cld.

Example 3.13

Let $X = \{p_1, q_1, r_1\}$, $\tau = \{\phi, \{p_1\}, \{q_1, r_1\}, X\}$ and $\mathcal{J} = \{\phi\}$. Then $\mathcal{J}^*C(X) = \{\phi, \{p_1\}, \{q_1, r_1\}, X\}$ and $\alpha GS C(X) = P(X)$. Here, $P = \{p_1, r_1\}$ is αg_s -cld but not \mathcal{J}^* -cld.

Proposition 3.14

Every \mathcal{J}^* -cld is αg -cld but converse is not true.

Proof

If P is a \mathcal{J}^* -cld subset of X and K is any open set containing P , since every open set is sg-open, we have $K \supseteq P^* \supseteq \alpha \text{cl}(P)$. Hence P is αg -cld.

Example 3.15

Let $X = \{p_1, q_1, r_1\}, \tau = \{\phi, \{r_1\}, \{p_1, q_1\}, X\}$ and $\mathcal{J} = \{\phi\}$. Then $\hat{I}C(X) = \{\phi, \{r_1\}, \{p_1, q_1\}, X\}$ and $\alpha GC(X) = P(X)$. Here, $P = \{p_1, r_1\}$ is α g-cld but not \mathcal{J}^* -cld.

Proposition 1.3.16

Every α -cld is \mathcal{J}^* - α -cld but converse is not true.

Proof

If P is an α -cld subset of X and K is any sg-open set containing P , we have $\alpha \text{ cl}(P^*) = P \subseteq K$. Hence P is \mathcal{J}^* - α -cld.

Example 3.17

Let $X = \{p_1, q_1, r_1\}, \tau = \{\phi, X, \{p_1, q_1\}\}$ and $\mathcal{J} = \{\phi\}$. Then $\alpha C(X) = \{\phi, \{r_1\}, X\}$ and $\mathcal{J}^* \alpha C(X) = \{\phi, \{r_1\}, \{p_1, r_1\}, \{q_1, r_1\}, X\}$. Clearly, the set $\{p_1, r_1\}$ is an $\mathcal{J}^* \alpha$ cld but not an α -cld.

Proposition 3.18

Every \mathcal{J}^* -cld is gs-cld but converse is not true.

Proof

If P is a \mathcal{J}^* -cld subset of X and K is any open set containing P , since every open set is sg-open, we have $K \supseteq P^* \supseteq \text{scl}(P)$. Hence P is gs-cld.

Example 3.19

Let $X = \{p_1, q_1, r_1\}, \tau = \{\phi, \{p_1\}, X\}$ and $\mathcal{J} = \{\phi\}$. Then $\mathcal{J}^* C(X) = \{\phi, \{q_1, r_1\}, X\}$ and $GS C(X) = \{\phi, \{q_1\}, \{r_1\}, \{p_1, q_1\}, \{p_1, r_1\}, \{q_1, r_1\}, X\}$. Here, $P = \{r_1\}$ is gs-cld but not \mathcal{J}^* -cld.

Proposition 3.20

Every \mathcal{J}^* -cld is gsp-cld but converse is not true.

Proof

If P is a \mathcal{J}^* -cld subset of X and K is any open set containing P , every open set is sg-open, we have $K \supseteq P^* \supseteq \text{spcl}(P)$. Hence P is gsp-cld.

Example 3.21

Let $X = \{p_1, q_1, r_1\}, \tau = \{\phi, \{q_1\}, X\}$ and $\mathcal{J} = \{\phi\}$. Then $\mathcal{J}^* C(X) = \{\phi, \{p_1, r_1\}, X\}$ and $GSP C(X) = \{\phi, \{p_1\}, \{r_1\}, \{p_1, q_1\}, \{p_1, r_1\}, \{q_1, r_1\}, X\}$. Here, $P = \{r_1\}$ is gsp-cld but not \mathcal{J}^* -cld.

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